

Infrared Studies of Some Chalcone Analogues. Assignment of Various Bands : Part II

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Received 1 February 1972

Infrared spectra of some substituted chalcones have been reported in the literature¹⁻⁴. We have studied the infrared spectra of ten chalcone analogues of the polynuclear series (Table 1) with the object of making assignments to various absorption bands. Our results are collected in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Compound No.	Ar	Substituents	Ar'
1	2-Naphthyl	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	
2	2-Naphthyl	2-Bromophenyl	
3	2-Naphthyl	5-Bromo-3,4-dimethoxy-phenyl	
4	2-Naphthyl	1-Naphthyl	
5	3-Nitro-4-hydroxy-1-naphthyl	5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-phenyl	
6	3-Nitro-4-hydroxy-1-naphthyl	5-Bromo-3,4-dimethoxy-phenyl	
7	3-Nitro-4-hydroxy-1-naphthyl	2-Bromophenyl	
8	3-Nitro-4-hydroxy-1-naphthyl	1-Naphthyl	
9	3-Nitro-4-hydroxy-1-naphthyl	2-Methylphenyl	
10	2-Phenanthryl	2,6-Dichlorophenyl	

EXPERIMENTAL

The chalcone analogues required for the study were prepared⁵ by the Claisen-Schmidt condensation of 2-acetonaphthone, 3-nitro-4-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthone and 2-acetylphenanthrene with various arylaldehydes, viz., 2,6-dichloro-, 2-bromo-, 5-bromo-3, 4-dimethoxy-, 5-bromo-2-hydroxy and 2-methylbenzaldehydes, and 1-naphthaldehyde. The

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TABLE 2
Infra-red absorption bands of chalcone analogues

Region cm ⁻¹	Mode of Vibration	OBSERVED BANDS, cm ⁻¹									
		1*	2*	3*	4*	5*	6*	7*	8*	9*	10*
3100-3000	ν CH (Aromatic)	3030	—	3049	3049	3067	3077	3077	3067	3058	3059
3000	ν CH (Olefin)	3030	3030	3003	3003	3003	2994	3012	3012	3012	3003
1685-1665	ν C = O	1656	1661	1667	1668	1681	1681	1684	1678	1678	1667
1647-1621	ν C = C	1629	1629	1626	1629	1639	1639	1647	1642	1642	1647
1650-1600	Skeletal vibn.	1629, 1610	1629, 1605	1595, 1504	1629, 1603	1639, 1613	1629, 1613	1616, 1603	1616, 1600	1626, 1613	1613, 1570
1630-1575	Condensed	1575, 1531	1585, 1515	1488, 1466	1592, 1572	1603, 1582	1603, 1582	1587, 1503	1587, 1572	1597, 1585	1527, 1497
1625-1450	Systems	1464, 1456	1484, 1473	—	1502, 1464	1502, 1468	1504, 1480	1488, 1456	1501, 1464	1499, 1484	1490, 1484
1600-1500	ν Phenylalkene	1550	1585, 1560	1595, 1563	1592, 1572	1592, 1548	1582, 1548	1582, 1548	1587, 1548	1585, 1546	1550
1548-1508	ν_{as} NO ₂	—	—	—	—	1548	1548	1548	1548	1546	—
1356-1340	ν_s NO ₂	—	—	—	—	1355	1355	1359	1357	1355	—
2850	ν_s CH ₃ (Ar-OCH ₃)	—	—	2825	—	2825	2825	—	—	—	—
1280	ν_{as} (=C-O-C)	—	—	1266	—	1268	—	—	—	—	—
1460	δ CH	—	—	1466	—	1460	—	—	—	—	—
1616-1598	ν Benzene ring	—	1605, 1585	—	—	—	1616, 1603	—	—	1613, 1597	—
1581-1573	—	—	1515	—	—	—	1587, 1456	—	—	1585, 1451	—
1510-1460	Vibn. (O-di	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1457-1427	Subtn.)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1380-1360	δ_s , CH ₃	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1355	—
1480-1450	δ_{as} CH ₃	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1451	—
1410-1310	δ OH(phenol)	—	—	—	—	1355	1355	1359	1357	1355	—
1260-1180	ν C-O (Phenol)	—	—	—	—	1258, 1239	1258, 1241	1261, 1242	1259, 1241	1256, 1239	—
1292-1272	ν C-C-C	1276	1294	1277	1272	1289, 1297	1289, 1295	1292, 1299	1290, 1299	1193, 1185	—
1175-1125	δ CH Substituted	1176, 1149	1272, 1215	—	1172, 1115	—	—	1261, 1242	1164, 1145	1256, 1239	1292, 1295
1110-1070	phenyl	1127, 1092	1190, 1074	—	1050, 1025	—	—	1098, 1075	1100, 1042	1193, 1185	1178, 1163
1070-1000	—	1100, 1025	1047, 1025	—	1009	—	—	1042, 1010	1008	1038, 1003	1144, 1095
1286-1252	δ Benzene	—	1272, 1166	—	—	—	—	1163, 1117	—	1256, 1161	1052, 1026
1164-1156	ring vibn.	—	1126, 1047	—	—	—	—	1163, 1117	—	1256, 1161	1001
1044-1022	O-di subtn.	—	1025	—	—	—	—	1042	—	1144, 1116	—
1057-1034	ν Ar-Cl(O-)	1045	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1038	—
1042-1028	ν Ar-Br(O-)	—	1047	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1052
980-965	γ CH	970	983	—	975	—	—	1042	—	—	—
below 900	γ CH	899, 869	841	951, 892	861, 849	891	891	892	892	982	899, 881
		854	859	859	859	—	—	—	—	890	866, 833

* Compound numbers correspond to those given in Table 1.
 ν = Stretching; δ = bending (in-plane); γ = bending (out-of-plane)
 Note: The region 820-720 cm⁻¹ has been obscured due to CHCl₃ absorption.

desired chalcone analogues were purified by repeated recrystallisation. The homogeneity of each compound was checked by thin-layer chromatography on silica gel using light petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (5 : 1) as developer solvents.

Infrared spectra were recorded in chloroform solution, 0.1 mm thickness, in the range 4000 cm^{-1} to 650 cm^{-1} on Beckman Model IR-7 precision prism-grating spectrometer.

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